

MOVING TOWARDS LIFE CYCLE THINKING BY INTEGRATING ADVANCED WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

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What would happen if citizen and companies were aware of the waste they generate, the impact of this on the environment and the human health and the management costs?

And what would happen if they participated in the proposal of initiatives to improve the efficiency of the service, if they paid waste management fees in accordance with waste generated and received incentives to foster sorting and waste prevention for reducing waste quantities and facilitating recycling?

Most probably, what would happen is that we could convert the current linear model into a new model based on the principles of the circular economy, a concept through which we would convert the origin of the problem into the solution.

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